

ISic0020

I.Sicily inscription 0020

Language

Latin

Type

honorific

Material

limestone

Object

plaque

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Panhormus

Place of origin (modern)

Palermo

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico Regionale Antonino Salinas,
inventory 3520

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Imp(eratori) · Caes(ari)

2. divi · Severi · Pii

3. nep(oti) · divi · Magn(i)

4. [---]

Apparatus

Text of IMusPalermo

Mommsen restores [Antonini filio].

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491780

EDR 137672

EDCS 22000864

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum*. Berlin. At 10.7278 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/item/buchseite/650789>)

Bivona, L. 1970. Iscrizioni latine lapidarie del Museo di Palermo. *Sikelia*. Palermo. At 20

Dessau, H. 1892-1916. Inscriptiones Latinae Selectae. Berlin. At 1655

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